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**Afaan Oromoo Audio Sentiment
Analysis Research Paper
Version 0.1.2**

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Date: Jan 28, 2024

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Abstract

This research delves into the linguistic and technological facets of the Afaan Oromo language, emphasizing its foundational elements, writing systems, and phonetic characteristics. The study further extends to sentiment analysis through two main experiments: raw audio data analysis and text-based analysis. These experiments are pivotal for understanding sentiment expression in Afaan Oromo, combining linguistic insights with advanced deep learning techniques.

The research methodology follows the Design Science Research Process (DSRP), addressing challenges in sentiment analysis through a systematic approach. The study includes a comprehensive dataset comprising 1000 labeled audio samples and 7000 labeled text samples in Afaan Oromo. Two main experiments are conducted, utilizing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for audio processing and exploring pretrained models for text-based sentiment analysis.

In the analysis of audio data, CNNs prove effective in capturing local patterns, achieving an accuracy of 90.41% and an F1 score of 90.59. Audio preprocessing methods, including spectrogram generation and data augmentation, contribute to the model's robustness. The text-based analysis, however, yields insights into the challenges of transcription models, with performance influenced by both the model and transcription accuracy.

The findings underscore the importance of considering data nature and context in sentiment analysis, suggesting potential avenues for future research, such as hybrid models combining audio and text representations for improved accuracy.

1. Introduction

Language is a powerful medium of expression, reflecting the emotions, opinions, and sentiments of individuals. In the digital age, the analysis of sentiment in audio data has gained prominence, enabling a deeper understanding of human communication. This research delves into sentiment analysis in the context of Afaan Oromo audio, a language with a diverse speaker population.

1.1 Motivation

In light of Ethiopia's rapid technological advancement and the escalating number of social media users, coupled with the surge in audio data sharing on these platforms, the need to discern the sentiment of audio data becomes increasingly imperative. The proliferation of social media has created an unprecedented volume of user-generated content, particularly in Afaan Oromo language, necessitating mechanisms to regulate and understand the sentiments expressed in these posts.

1.1.1 Technological Advancement in Ethiopia

Ethiopia's stride towards technological modernization has resulted in a significant increase in online activities, with a growing number of individuals engaging in social media platforms. The advent of advanced technologies has facilitated the seamless sharing of audio content, contributing to the richness and diversity of online communication.

1.1.2 Escalating Social Media Users

The surge in social media users presents both opportunities and challenges. As the online community expands, so does the need to comprehend the sentiments embedded in audio posts. Understanding the emotional tone of content shared on social media is crucial for various purposes, including content regulation, targeted advertising, and online business operations.

1.1.3 Rise of Audio Data Sharing

The prevalence of audio data sharing through social media platforms is on the rise. Users are increasingly expressing themselves through voice messages, creating a dynamic landscape of linguistic content. Analyzing sentiment in Afaan Oromo audio posts is essential not only for regulatory purposes but also for harnessing the potential of this medium for business and advertising.

1.1.4 Regulating Posts and Advertisement

Identifying sentiment in audio data is pivotal for post regulation and advertisement strategies. This enables platforms to maintain a positive and inclusive online environment by addressing potentially harmful or offensive content. Moreover, businesses can tailor their advertising approaches based on the sentiments prevalent in user-generated audio posts, enhancing the effectiveness of online marketing efforts.

1.1.5 Countering Hate Spread in Afaan Oromo Language

One of the critical challenges posed by the rapid growth of social media is the potential spread of hate speech. Analyzing sentiments in Afaan Oromo language posts allows for the proactive identification and mitigation of hate speech, fostering a safer online space for users. By understanding the sentiment dynamics, measures can be taken to curb the dissemination of harmful content and promote digital ethics.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite the abundance of Afaan Oromo audio data, the absence of specialized sentiment analysis models poses a challenge. This research aims to address this gap by developing a machine-learning model capable of accurately detecting sentiment in Afaan Oromo audio recordings.

1.3 Research Questions

1. How can machine learning techniques be effectively applied to sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio data?
2. What challenges and nuances are specific to sentiment analysis in the Afaan Oromo language?
3. How can the developed model accommodate the diverse range of speakers within the Afaan Oromo community?
4. What distinguishes the morphological structure of Afaan Oromo from that of other languages?
5. Is it possible to apply transfer learning from another language to enhance sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo?
6. How does the dataset impact the performance of the learning model?
7. What differentiates audio sentiment analysis from other sentiment analysis techniques, such as text sentiment analysis, in terms of metrics?

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 General Objective

To develop a robust machine learning model for sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo data.

1.4.2 Specific Objective

To identify and address the unique challenges posed by sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio data, considering the diverse set of speakers within the language community.

1.5 Significance

This research is significant in providing a tailored solution for sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio, making sentiment analysis tools more accessible to a wider audience.

1.6 Contribution

The primary contribution of this research resides in the creation of a dedicated sentiment analysis model tailored to Afaan Oromo audio. This advancement not only pushes the boundaries of sentiment analysis but also deepens our comprehension within the realm of linguistically diverse contexts. The model, developed through meticulous training with various machine learning algorithms, holds significant potential.

This research extends beyond academic pursuits, as the model can serve as a valuable tool for studying the intricacies of the Afaan Oromo language. Furthermore, the model's versatility allows its integration into social media platforms, functioning either as an extension or through the provision of a model API. This innovation opens avenues for individuals and organizations aiming to establish social media environments that are free from hate speech and disruptive content. By leveraging the capabilities of the developed model, efforts can be directed toward fostering online spaces that prioritize positive user experiences and contribute to a more inclusive digital community.

1.7 Scope

The scope of this research encompasses the development and evaluation of a machine-learning model specifically designed for sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio recordings.

1.8 Thesis Structure

The thesis will be organized into distinct chapters, including a comprehensive literature review, detailed methodology, model development, evaluation, and concluding remarks, each contributing to the overall understanding of sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Foundations

This section will discuss the important foundations that are needed for the proposed solution.

2.1.1 Deep Learning (DL)

Deep Learning stands as a cornerstone within the broader field of machine learning, propelling AI systems to new heights of complexity and sophistication. At its core, DL involves neural networks with multiple layers, enabling machines to learn hierarchical representations of data. This approach has proven immensely successful in tasks such as image recognition, speech processing, and language understanding. Understanding DL is essential for any AI practitioner, offering a powerful toolkit to unravel intricate patterns and make informed decisions based on vast datasets.

2.1.2 Natural Language Processing (NLP)

In the realm of human-computer interaction, Natural Language Processing emerges as a transformative force. NLP equips machines with the ability to comprehend, interpret, and generate human language, bridging the gap between human communication and artificial intelligence. From chatbots that engage in natural conversations to language translation systems, NLP plays a crucial role in making AI systems more accessible and user-friendly. For professionals like Abdulkarim Getachew Mohammed, specializing in AI, a deep understanding of NLP opens avenues to contribute to cutting-edge language-driven applications and technologies.

As we navigate the intricate landscape of AI concepts, we recognize the dynamic interplay between Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing. These concepts not only represent technological milestones but also hold the potential to shape the future of AI applications. For someone with ambitions like Abdulkarim, this knowledge serves as a compass in steering the course of a career that transcends borders, aligning with the global advancements in the field of Artificial Intelligence.

2.2 Related Works

Sentiment analysis, the task of discerning emotions, opinions, or attitudes expressed in textual or audio data, has gained significant attention in recent years. While extensive research has been conducted in sentiment analysis for major languages, there is a noticeable gap when it comes to underrepresented languages such as Afan Oromo. Afan Oromo, spoken by millions in East Africa, presents a unique linguistic and cultural context that demands tailored sentiment analysis solutions.

The scarcity of resources and research in sentiment analysis for Afan Oromo, particularly in the audio domain, calls for focused exploration. The challenges involve addressing the limited availability of annotated datasets, understanding the language's nuances, and developing effective models that capture sentiment expressions in spoken form.

Several studies have explored sentiment analysis in resource-scarce languages, emphasizing the need for culturally sensitive approaches. Research efforts have touched upon sentiment lexicon creation,

acoustic feature extraction, and machine learning model development to suit the linguistic characteristics of underrepresented languages.

2.2.1 Audio-based sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo Language

Despite an extensive exploration of sentiment analysis in various languages, a noticeable gap exists in the direct exploration of Afaan Oromo sentiment analysis in audio. The dearth of research specifically addressing sentiment in spoken Afaan Oromo presents a unique opportunity for investigation. In the absence of direct studies, we draw parallels and insights from a closely related research paper, "Speech-based Question and Question Answering Classification," which although distinct in its focus, provides valuable foundations for sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio.

The current literature lacks a dedicated investigation into sentiment analysis in spoken Afaan Oromo, making it crucial to explore related studies that touch upon aspects of speech processing and analysis. The paper mentioned above primarily delves into question and answering classification using speech data, showcasing advancements in speech recognition technology. While its primary focus differs from sentiment analysis, the methodologies and techniques employed for speech-based tasks can be leveraged and adapted for sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo audio.

The aforementioned research paper, while not directly addressing Afaan Oromo sentiment analysis, offers insights into the intricacies of processing and understanding spoken language. The techniques presented for live speech recognition, acoustic modeling, and language modeling can serve as foundational elements for Afaan Oromo sentiment analysis in audio.

Adapting the methodologies used for question and answering classification to sentiment analysis involves repurposing the speech recognition system to identify emotional nuances in spoken Afaan Oromo. The configuration, acoustic model paths, and language model paths outlined in the paper provide a starting point for building a tailored sentiment analysis system for the Afaan Oromo language.

In conclusion, the absence of dedicated studies on Afaan Oromo sentiment analysis in audio motivates us to draw upon related research in speech-based tasks, recognizing the potential to bridge this gap and contribute to the field of sentiment analysis in underrepresented languages.

2.2.2 Text-based sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo Language

Afaan Oromo, a prominent language in Ethiopia, presents challenges in hate speech detection on social media platforms. The language's complexity necessitates nuanced approaches to detection. Datasets are gathered from platforms like Facebook, containing posts and comments, which are then categorized into hate speech and free speech classes based on predefined criteria. Machine learning models demonstrate higher accuracy with word embeddings in hate speech detection. Future efforts may explore multimodal detection techniques and linguistic diversity in hate speech detection.(1)

Previous studies have laid the foundation for text-based sentiment analysis in Afaan Oromo. One notable work by Obsa Gelchu Horsa and Kula Kekeba Tune introduces aspect-based sentiment

analysis (ABSA) for Afaan Oromoo movie reviews using various machine-learning techniques. The study collected a dataset of 2800 Afaan Oromoo movie reviews from YouTube and applied machine learning algorithms such as random forest, logistic regression, support vector machine (SVM), and multinomial naive Bayes (MNB) for sentiment analysis. The experiments utilized bag of words (BoW) and TF-IDF feature extraction techniques to evaluate the performance of the models. The results indicated promising accuracy and F1-score values across different algorithms, highlighting the potential of ABSA for analyzing sentiment in Afaan Oromoo movie reviews.(2)

Furthermore, research by M. Oljira explored sentiment analysis for Afaan Oromoo using a combined convolutional neural network and bidirectional long short-term memory (CNN-BLSTM) architecture. This study delved into document- and sentence-level sentiment analysis, contributing to the understanding of sentiment expression in Afaan Oromoo text.(2)

Additionally, N. B. Defersha and K. K. Tune investigated the detection of hate speech in Afaan Oromo social media using machine learning approaches. Although the primary focus was on identifying hate speech, the study underscores the importance of understanding sentiment in textual data written in Afaan Oromo.(2)

2.2.3 Multilingual Papers

2.2.3.1 Text-based Sentiment Analysis in Multilingual Contexts

The Master's Thesis authored by Abrhalei Frezghi Tela, titled "Sentiment Analysis for Low-Resource Language: The Case of Tigrinya," makes a substantial contribution to the field of sentiment analysis, particularly for languages encountering resource limitations. Tela's focus on Tigrinya, a low-resource language-sharing challenge with Afaan Oromo, provides valuable insights essential for shaping sentiment analysis models for the latter.

In the multilingual landscape, Tela's thesis establishes a foundation for exploring common methodologies and transfer learning techniques applicable to various low-resource languages. The effective strategies unveiled for sentiment analysis in Tigrinya lay the groundwork for similar endeavors in Afaan Oromo and other languages confronting resource constraints.

Tela's work showcases the potential for knowledge transfer and collaborative efforts among researchers dedicated to sentiment analysis in underrepresented languages, promoting a nuanced understanding of sentiment within diverse linguistic contexts.

While Tela's research forms a solid basis for sentiment analysis in low-resource languages, including Afaan Oromo, the shift from text-based to audio sentiment analysis demands careful exploration and potential adjustments. This emphasizes the continual necessity for research addressing the intricacies of sentiment analysis in diverse linguistic settings, ensuring that progress is transferable and relevant to the distinct challenges posed by different language modalities.

2.2.3.2 Audio-based Sentiment Analysis in Multilingual Contexts

Multilingual sentiment analysis in the context of audio processing has gained considerable attention as researchers explore diverse languages and cultures. Drawing insights from the findings of

"Cross-Corpus Multilingual Speech Emotion Recognition: Amharic vs. Other Languages," this literature review will delve into the specific domain of sentiment analysis in audio, with a focus on the Afan Oromo language.

The aforementioned research highlights the challenges and opportunities in multilingual speech emotion recognition. It provides valuable insights into the cross-corpus experiments involving languages such as Amharic, English, German, and Urdu. Understanding the nuances of emotion recognition in various languages lays a foundation for exploring similar patterns in sentiment analysis.

2.2.3.2.1 Cross-Cultural Variances in Speech Emotion

The study emphasizes the cross-cultural differences observed in speech emotion recognition, suggesting varying levels of difficulty for different languages. These insights serve as a backdrop for exploring how cultural and linguistic diversity may influence sentiment expression in the Afan Oromo language.

2.2.3.2.2 Leveraging Cross-Lingual Approaches

Experiments presented in the research paper demonstrate the effectiveness of cross-lingual and multilingual approaches in creating sentiment analysis systems, especially in languages with limited training data. Such methodologies provide a framework for considering similar strategies in the development of sentiment analysis models for Afan Oromo.

2.2.3.2.3 Importance of Dataset Composition

The research underscores the significance of dataset composition in training sentiment analysis models. The availability of the Amharic Speech Emotion Dataset (ASED) and its impact on model performance serves as a valuable reference. This highlights the importance of creating dedicated datasets, potentially similar to ASED, for sentiment analysis in Afan Oromo.

2.2.3.2.4 Future Directions and Challenges

As suggested in the original research, future work may involve improving sentiment analysis performance when training on non-target languages. The applicability of these suggestions to Afan Oromo sentiment analysis can guide researchers in addressing specific challenges and enhancing the overall effectiveness of sentiment recognition in audio data.

In summary, leveraging insights from the cross-corpus multilingual experiments, this literature review sets the stage for exploring sentiment analysis in audio data for the Afan Oromo language. The challenges, methodologies, and findings discussed in the original research provide a valuable framework for advancing research in sentiment analysis within the context of Afan Oromo.

3. Afaan Oromo Language

3.1 Overview

Comprehending the linguistic framework is imperative for facilitating the development of the proposed prototype. This chapter elucidates the foundational structure of Afaan Oromo, encompassing an exploration of the language's inherent characteristics. The discussion encompasses the language's prevalence, and its diverse applications across mediums like newspapers, various Oromia states' offices, various research publications, and higher educational institutions. Additionally, the chapter delves into the mechanisms governing word formation, the morphological composition, and other pivotal facets of the language essential for the contextual relevance of this thesis.

3.2 Foundational Aspects of the Afaan Oromo Language

The Oromo community, indigenous to the northeastern part of Africa, stands as the predominant ethnic group within Ethiopia. A considerable portion of Ethiopia's population and landmass is concentrated in the Oromia region. Recognized as the third-largest language in Africa, Afaan Oromo, synonymous with the Oromo language, boasts a speaker base exceeding 50 million individuals across Ethiopia, Kenya, Somalia, and Egypt. Interestingly, its prevalence extends beyond Ethiopia, with Afaan Oromo actively spoken and taught in various urban centers across the United States, Australia, Canada, and Europe. Foreign individuals expressing interest in Afaan Oromo can engage through dedicated language classes.

As the official language of the Oromia region, Afaan Oromo distinguishes itself by being written in both the Latin script and possessing its unique script. The Oromo people, adherents to Islam, Christianity, and traditional religions like Waaqeffannaa, present a diverse religious landscape. The linguistic spectrum of the Oromo encompasses Afaan Oromo, Amharic, Tigrinya, Gurage, and Omotic.

Afaan Oromo transcends national boundaries, finding expression not only in Ethiopia but also in Kenya and Somalia. It holds official status in the Oromia Regional State and serves as a medium of instruction in educational institutions, spanning from schools to colleges and universities, both domestically and internationally. The language assumes a central role in academic pursuits, featuring as a major course at various academic levels, including Bachelor's, Master's, and PhD programs in Ethiopian universities. Notably, it is also taught at institutions like North American Minneapolis College.

Moreover, Afaan Oromo enjoys representation in diverse media platforms, with radio and television programs disseminating information in the language. Ethiopian Radio, Radio Fana, Oromia Television, Ethiopian Television (ETV), and Fana Television actively contribute to the linguistic landscape. The script evolution of Afaan Oromo, transitioning from the Ge'ez script before 1991 to the Qubee alphabet with a Latin foundation, marks a significant milestone. With 26 consonants and 10 vowels, the language embodies a rich oral heritage, complemented by an array of literary works and contemporary arts, including music and folk arts.

3.3 Afaan Oromo Writing System and Phonetics

Afaan Oromo holds a distinguished status as one of the official working languages in Ethiopia, extending its reach to several states within the federal structure, including Oromia, Harari, and Dire Dawa, as well as the Oromia Zone in the Amhara Region. It assumes a pivotal role in education, particularly in Oromia, Harari, and the Oromia Zone. Additionally, Afaan Oromo is utilized on federal websites alongside other languages.

3.3.1 Afaan Oromo Writing Systems

Afaan Oromo, being a phonetic language, adheres to a simple and consistent writing system based on the Latin alphabet. Unlike English or other Latin languages, there are no skipped or mispronounced consonants or alphabets in Afaan Oromo. Each alphabet, known as "qubee," is pronounced distinctly with either clear short or quick sounds, or long and stretched sounds. This phonetic clarity is especially noticeable in words with doubled consonants. Furthermore, when vowels are duplicated in a word, they are pronounced with lengthened or stretched sounds.

Afaan Oromo comprises both vowels and consonants, similar to English. The language features five vowels: a, e, i, o, and u. When pronounced in lengthened or stretched forms, these vowels are denoted as 'aa,' 'ee,' 'ii,' 'oo,' and 'uu' respectively. The consonants in Afaan Oromo closely resemble those in English, with unique additions such as "ch," "dh," "sh," "ny," "ph," "ts," "zh," and " (hudhaa)." Notably, "ch" and "sh" are articulated similarly to their English counterparts.

Specifically, the Afaan Oromo consonant "dh" is formed akin to the English "d," with a slight curling of the tongue back, producing a glottal stop audible before the next vowel. The consonant "ny" involves smacking the lips outward, akin to the English "gn" sound.

These unique letter combinations contribute to the formation of words. For example, "ch" signifies "eating" in "nyaachuu," "sh" represents "five," "dh" is used for "dhaabachuu" meaning "stop," and "ph" indicates "buuphaa" translating to "egg." In total, the Afaan Oromo writing system consists of 33 letters known as "Qubee," including 28 consonants and 5 vowels.

3.3.1.1 Qubee (Sagaleewwan) dubbii Afaan Oromo in Capital and Small:

A	a	B	b	C	c	D	d	E	e	F	f	G	g	H	h
I	i	J	j	K	k	L	l	M	m	N	n	O	o	P	p
Q	q	R	r	S	s	T	t	U	u	V	v	W	w	X	x

Y	y	Z	z	CH	ch	DH	dh	NY	ny	PH	ph	SH	sh	'(hudha)	
---	---	---	---	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----------	--

This table provides a comprehensive overview of the Qubee alphabet in both capital and small forms, encompassing vowels and consonants crucial to Afaan Oromo's written expression.

3.3.1.2 Grammar in Afaan Oromo

The Afaan Oromo alphabet holds paramount importance as individuals in everyday life utilize its structure for both written and spoken communication. Mastery of this alphabet is indispensable, as correct pronunciation relies on a clear understanding of each letter. Accurate pronunciation enhances mutual understanding when conversing in Afaan Oromo.

Afaan Oromo adheres to a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) structure, where the subject is followed by the object and then the verb. Although the language allows for flexible word order due to its declined nature (nouns vary based on their function in the sentence), the consistent placement of verbs after subjects and objects is a notable characteristic. Generally, indirect objects are positioned after direct objects in Afaan Oromo sentences.

Moreover, Afaan Oromo exhibits a prevalence of prepositions and postpositions, contributing to the language's nuanced expression. Understanding and adhering to these rules enhance the clarity and precision of communication in both written and spoken contexts.

3.3.1.3 Afaan Oromo Vowels (Dubbachiiftuu):

The five vowels— a, e, o, u, and i—form an essential component of Afaan Oromo pronunciation. Vowels are pronounced similarly, with variations in opening and closing depending on stress. For instance:

- a: Pronounced powerfully and clearly, as seen in words like dhagaa, bara, macaafa, jalqabaa, afaan.
- e: Pronounced with emphasis, whether in an open form as in Seensa, Seena, Keenya, Beekuu.
- i: Exhibits a distinct pronunciation, emphasized in words like Fidi, irraa, Xinnoo, biyya, Hoojii.
- o: Stressed and pronounced sharply, as demonstrated in Gooftaa, Tokko, Yeroo, Kiyyoo, Boodde.
- u: Clear and powerful pronunciation, observed in words like oduu, umaa, xumura, and others.

This consistent and intentional pronunciation of vowels contributes to the clarity and emphasis of spoken Afaan Oromo words.

3.3.1.4 Afaan Oromo Consonants - Dubbifamaa

The consonant system in Afaan Oromo, known as Dubbifamaa, shares similarities with Italian, yet it includes distinctive exceptions and unique combinations. The following table outlines the consonants in Afaan Oromo:

Labial	Alveolar/Retroflex	Palato-alveolar	Velar	Glottal
--------	--------------------	-----------------	-------	---------

Nasal	m	n	ɲ ⟨ny⟩	
Plosive/Affricate	voiceless (p)	t	tʃ ⟨ch⟩	k
	voiced b	d	dʒ ⟨j⟩	g
	ejective	p' ⟨ph⟩	t' ⟨x⟩	tʃ' ⟨c⟩
	implosive	ɗ ⟨dh⟩		
Fricative	voiceless	f	s	ʃ ⟨sh⟩
	voiced (v)		z	
Approximant	w	l	j ⟨y⟩	
Rhotic	r			

This consonant chart provides an overview of the Afaan Oromo consonants, showcasing their articulation points and distinctive features. It's worth noting that the language incorporates ejective and implosive sounds, contributing to its phonetic

Most Afaan Oromo consonants align with those in Italian, with unique combinations and exceptions. Labial, alveolar/retroflex, palato-alveolar, velar, and glottal consonants contribute to the language's phonetic diversity.

Afaan Oromo Double Consonants:

Double consonant combinations are present in stressed Afaan Oromo words, except for the combinations ny, dh, ph, and sh.

Afaan Oromo Stress:

Stress in Afaan Oromo typically falls on the final syllable in most words, with some exceptions where the first syllable is stressed. Examples include "gammoojjii," "ijoollummaa," and "ilaallu."

3.3.1.5 List of Stop-Words

-	(	)	dhaw	wanna	bakka
wagga	addaa	afoo	faana	eesa	eessa

eessaa	eenyu	cinaa	dura	duratti	duraa
adda	olee	ol	oli	maashaa	manee
adaa	lamaan	dur	arba	hidh	seen
hat	gad	gadi	guh	eeg	ejj
maq	baadh	fil	fuuldura	if	hed
jala	jir	jira	jiru	jidduu	dhiig
dhug	durs	duru	buh	gam	diig
aad	beek	erg	yaad	agarsiiso	o
akka	akkam	akkasuma	s	akkaamitt	i
akkum	akkuma	akkanaa	ala	alatti	alla
amma	ammaa	ammaatti	ammaaf	ammaas	ammo
ammoo	an	ana	anee	ani	anaaf
attam	ati	bira	booda	booddee	dabalatee
s	dha	dhaan	dudduuba	dugda	dura
duuba	eega	eegana	eegasii	enaa	erga
ergii	f	faallaa	fagaatee	fi	fullee
fuullee	gajjallaa	gama	gararraa	garas	garuu

giddu	gidduu	gubbaa	ha	hallettuu	hata`u
hatahuuyy	u	hamma	haga	hanga	83
hangahen	na	henna	hoggaa	hogguu	hoo
idda	illee	immoo	in	ini	innaa
inni	irra	irraa	irraan	isa	isaa
isaaf	isaan	isaani	isaanii	isaaniitiin	isaanirraa
isaanitti	isaatiin	isarraa	isatti	isee	iseen
ishee	isheen	isheen	ishii	ishiif	ishiin
ishiirraa	ishiitti	isii	isiin	isin	isini
isinii	isiniif	isiniin	isindirraa	isinitti	ittaanee
itti	ittiin	itumallee	ituu	ituullee	jala
jalatti	jara	jecha	jechaan	jechoota	jechuu
jechuun	kkf	kkfn	ka	kam	kan
kana	kanneen	kanamale	es	kanaa	kanaaf
kanaafi	kanaafuu	kanaan	kanaatiin	kanaatti	karaa
kee	keef	ke	kees	keenya	keenyyaa
keessa	keessan	keessaan	keessatti	keeti	keetii

kiyya	ko	koo	kootu	kun	kunneen
kunniin	kunis	kuniis	lafa	lama	lachuu
maal	malee	maaliif	manna	maqaa	mataakoo
moo	na	naa	naaf	naan	naannoo
nama	narraa	natti	nu	nuti	nu`i
nuhi	nurraa	nuti	nutti	nuu	nuuf
nuun	nuy	nuyi	obbo	obboo	odoo
ofii	of	oggaa	oo	osoo	84
otoo	otuma	otumallee	otuu	otuullee	qullii
qofa	sanaan	saaniif	sadii	sana	sun
sanneen	sunniin	saniif	si	si`i	sii
siif	sin	siin	silaa	simmoo	sinitti
siqee	sirraa	sitti	sun	ta`e	ta`u
ta`an	tahan	tahe	tahee	tahuu	ta`uu
tahullee	ta`ullee	tana	tanaaf	tanaafi	tanaafuu
tahullee	tahuyyu	tahuyyuu	tawullee	teenya	teessan
ti	tiyya	too	tii	unu	utuu

waahee	waa`ee	waa	waan	waggaa	wajjin
wal	walirraa	walii	waliin	walitti	warra
warri	woo	yaa	yammuu	yemmuu	yeroo
yommii	yommuu	yoo	yookaan	ykn	yookiin
yookiini	moo				

3.3.2 Afaan Oromo Phonetics

In Text-to-Speech (TTS) and Speech-to-Text (STT) systems, understanding a language's grapheme-to-phoneme correlation is vital for converting written (grapheme) words into their spoken (phoneme) forms. Afaan Oromo's phonetic characteristics, encompassing voicing, tongue position, tongue height, place of articulation, and method of articulation, contribute to defining its phone set.

Afaan Oromo's alphabet augments letters for the five vowel sounds, reflecting the Southern Cushitic arrangement of five short and five long vowels. The contrastive length plays a crucial role, as seen in examples like "bara" (year) and "baraa" (know). Consonant gemination, or the lengthening of a consonant, further distinguishes words, as illustrated in "bara" (year) and "barraa" (knowing).

Distinct from many languages, Afaan Oromo places emphasis on the tone-bearing unit rather than the syllable's vowel. Two mora make up a long vowel or diphthong, each capable of having high or low tones. Notably, only one high tone is allowed per word, positioned on the last or next-to-last mora.

The language employs three tones—rising, falling, and high—each governed by specific rules:

- a. A falling tone results from a sequence of high-low notes over a long vowel.
- b. A low-high sequence manifests as high-high on long vowels.

This tone-based technique, resembling a pitch accent, aligns with Somali linguistic practices. Tone in Afaan Oromo is intertwined with stress: decreasing tone indicates less stress, low tone signifies none, and high tone conveys substantial stress.

In written Afaan Oromo, tone is denoted using specific accents:

- Acute accent (´): Indicates a high tone.
- Grave accent (`): Signifies a low tone.
- Circumflex (^): Represents a falling tone.

3.4 Script and Orthography

The initial rendition of Afaan Oromo was transcribed using the Ethiopian alphabet employed for Tigrinya, Amharic, and Classical Ethiopian. However, in 1974, it underwent a transformative shift to a Latin-based script known as Qubee. This script comprises a total of 31 symbols, including 5 digraphs (represented in square brackets with their equivalents in the International Phonetic Alphabet).

Key Features of the Qubee Script

1. Double Vowels: Used to denote long vowels. Long consonants are also expressed by doubling unless written as a digraph.
2. Additional Letters (p, z, and v): These letters are present in various dialects and loanwords.
3. Glottalized and Implosive Stops: Represented by [p'] for ph, [t'] for x, [dʒ] for dh, and [k'] for q.
4. Glottal Stop Indicator: An apostrophe is utilized to denote the glottal stop [ʔ].
5. Affricates: Shown as [tʃ] for ch, [dʒ] for j, and [tʃ] for c.
6. Fricative [ʃ]: Represented with the digraph sh.
7. Nasal [ɲ]: The digraph ny stands in for the nasal [ɲ].

This Qubee script offers a phonetically comprehensive representation of Afaan Oromo, accommodating its distinct sounds and linguistic nuances.

A a	B b	C c	Ch ch	D d	Dh dh	E e	F f	G g
a	ba	ca	cha	da	dha	e	fa	ga
[e]	[b]	[tʃ]	[tʃ]	[d]	[dʒ]	[ɛ]	[f]	[g]
H h	I i	J j	K k	L l	M m	N n	Ny ny	O o
ha	i	ja	ka	la	ma	na	nya	o
[h]	[i]	[dʒ]	[k]	[l]	[m]	[n]	[ɲ]	[ɔ]
P p	Ph ph	Q q	R r	S s	Sh sh	T t	U u	V v
pa	pha	qa	ra	sa	sha	ta	u	va
[p]	[pʰ]	[kʰ]	[r]	[s]	[ʃ]	[t]	[u]	[v]
W w	X x	Y y	Z z	'				
wa	xa	ya	za					
[w]	[x]	[j]	[z]	[ʔ]				
aa	ee	ii	oo	uu				
[a:]	[e:]	[i:]	[o:]	[u:]				

4. Methodology

4.1 Data Acquisition

For our Afaan Oromoo Audio Sentiment Analysis project, we adopted a comprehensive approach to gather diverse datasets. The datasets were sourced through a combination of in-house preparation, external collections from the internet, and leveraging data from Facebook. Our team prepared datasets by curating Afaan Oromoo text files labeled with sentiments (negative, neutral, and positive). Additionally, we obtained datasets from online sources, Facebook, and volunteer contributions to enhance the variety and depth of our project.

To provide a detailed insight into the audio dataset:

- The audio recordings cover various scenarios, including scripted conversations, spontaneous dialogues, and emotional monologues, with an average length of 20 seconds.
- The audio data was primarily gathered using Text-to-Speech (TTS) methodology, employing a Language Model (LLM) from Facebook Research. This model successfully converts Afaan Oromoo text to Afaan Oromoo audio, contributing to the diversity and richness of our audio dataset.
- A significant portion of our audio data is sourced from the "Afaan Oromoo Text-to-Speech Dataset" available on Mendeley Data. This dataset, although initially unlabelled, serves as a valuable resource that we labeled and converted to audio.
- The process involved converting the text in the dataset to English, using a pretrained model to label the English text, and then using this label to annotate the original Afaan Oromoo text.
- Volunteers also contributed to the audio dataset, providing varied accents and contributing to the overall dataset diversity.

Audio Datasets: Consisting of 1000 labeled audio samples, with sentiments categorized as negative, positive, and neutral. The dataset was split into 80% training and 20% testing subsets to facilitate model training and evaluation.

Text Datasets: Comprising 7000 labeled text samples in Afaan Oromoo, categorized into negative, positive, and neutral sentiments. Similar to the audio dataset, the text dataset was partitioned into 80% training and 20% testing subsets.

Preprocessing

Upon the collection of data, our preprocessing methodology is seamlessly integrated into the training pipeline, aligning with an automated and efficient approach developed by [183]. This preprocessing workflow contains four essential parts, ensuring the datasets are optimized for subsequent model training:

1. Text Data Preprocessing:

- **Stop Words Removal:** Common stop words were systematically removed to reduce noise and improve the representation of significant words.

- **Stigmatization and Lemmatization:** Both stemming and lemmatization techniques were applied to standardize word forms, ensuring consistency in the representation of semantically related words.
- **Tokenization:** The textual data was tokenized, breaking down sentences or paragraphs into individual tokens. This step is crucial for creating a structured input for subsequent analysis.

2. Audio Data Preprocessing:

- **Noise Removal:** To enhance the signal-to-noise ratio, a noise removal process was applied to the audio data, eliminating unwanted background noise and focusing on essential speech features.
- **Data Augmentation:** Augmentation techniques were employed to artificially increase the diversity of the audio dataset. This includes varying pitch, speed, and other relevant parameters to simulate real-world variations in speech.

This holistic approach to preprocessing not only improves the overall quality of the datasets but also contributes to the robustness and generalization capability of the subsequent sentiment analysis model. The integration of automated preprocessing within the training pipeline aligns with best practices, streamlining the workflow for efficiency and effectiveness.

4.1 Research Methodology

To ensure a systematic and effective approach to addressing the challenges of Afaan Oromoo Audio Sentiment Analysis, our research methodology follows the Design Science Research Process (DSRP). This structured methodology aligns well with our goal of addressing an existing problem and designing a new method to solve it. The DSRP method consists of six major steps: Problem Identification & Motivation, Objective Formulation, Design and Development, Demonstration, Evaluation, and Communication. However, in our case, the Demonstration and Evaluation steps were combined into a single step called Evaluation, as our evaluation involved assessing the performance gains of the proposed architecture.

1. Problem Identification & Motivation:

- **Problem Definition:** The motivation for our work stemmed from the existing problem of accuracy-speed trade-off in sentiment analysis models. We clearly defined the problem as redundant computations on input that do not require further transformation, resulting in extra cost.
- **Literature Review:** A comprehensive literature review was conducted, examining survey articles, seminal publications on major deep learning architectures, and related works addressing the challenges in sentiment analysis. The focus was on existing solutions utilizing CNN, RNN, BERT, and LSTM architectures

2. Objective Formulation:

- **General Objective:** The overarching goal of this research project is to enhance the efficiency of sentiment analysis models by mitigating the accuracy-speed trade-off through innovative model design and optimization techniques.
- **Specific Objectives:** Defined specific objectives include exploring and implementing improvements in CNN, RNN, BERT, and LSTM architectures to reduce redundant computations, enhance speed, and maintain or improve accuracy.

3. Design & Prototyping Iteration:

- **Brainstorming Sessions:** Building upon insights from the literature review, brainstorming sessions were conducted to generate design ideas for optimizing existing sentiment analysis models without incorporating reinforcement learning. The focus was on refining CNN, RNN, BERT, and LSTM architectures.
- **Prototyping & Iteration:** Rapid prototyping and iteration were employed to experiment with different design ideas for different models, ensuring that the proposed modifications align with the objective of improving efficiency without introducing unnecessary complexity.

4. Evaluation:

- **Testing Hyperparameters:** Initially, the finalized design modifications were tested by adjusting hyperparameters on models employing different architectures. The aim was to understand the impact of these adjustments on computational efficiency and sentiment analysis performance.
- **Performance Assessment:** Using optimized hyperparameters, the modified models were evaluated on state-of-the-art benchmarks to assess their effectiveness in achieving the desired balance between accuracy and speed. Additionally, the applicability of the optimized models in transfer learning scenarios was explored.
- **Identification of Limitations:** Through the evaluation process, potential limitations of the optimized models were identified. This led to further refinement and the introduction of specific post-training optimization techniques to address these limitations and enhance overall model performance.

5. Knowledge Contribution:

- **Analysis of Results:** The results and the architecture were analyzed to identify key findings and contributions. These findings were derived from the evaluations conducted during the Evaluation stage.
- **Performance and Efficiency Reports:** Key contributions included performance and efficiency reports, showcasing the advancements made in sentiment analysis for Afaan Oromoo language.
- **Insights About Model Operation:** Insights were provided about how the model works, adding to the body of knowledge in sentiment analysis and deep learning applications.

This comprehensive research methodology, rooted in the DSRP, allowed for a systematic progression from problem identification to the development and evaluation of a novel solution, contributing valuable insights to the field of Afaan Oromoo Audio Sentiment Analysis.

5. Experimentations

5.1 Overview

Currently we have two main experiments;

- Analyze the raw audio data
- Text based analysis
 - Convert audio to text and do the analysis on the text
 - Do the analysis on the original text data

Although we might include other experimentation, currently these two main categories are the two main experimentations we have conducted so far.

5.2 Analyzing Audio Data

In this experimentation, we will train a neural network on the raw audio data. In our project, we employed Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for audio processing due to their effectiveness in capturing local patterns and hierarchical representations in spectrogram-like data.

5.3 Audio Preprocessing Methods

Effective audio preprocessing is essential for extracting meaningful features and enhancing model performance. Some of the key preprocessing steps implemented in our project include:

Spectrogram Generation: Converting audio signals into spectrograms provides a visual representation of the frequency content over time, serving as input to the CNN.

Normalization: Scaling the spectrogram values to a standardized range ensures uniformity and aids in model convergence during training.

Data Augmentation: Introducing variations in pitch, speed, and background noise during training enhances the model's robustness and generalization capabilities.

Feature Extraction: Extracting relevant features, such as Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs), can further improve the model's ability to capture nuanced patterns in audio data.

5.3.1 Choice of Neural Network Architecture

CNNs have proven success in image processing tasks, making them a suitable choice for audio analysis, as audio data can be represented as spectrograms, which are analogous to images. CNNs excel in learning spatial hierarchies, allowing them to capture intricate patterns in both the time and frequency domains. The local receptive fields of convolutional layers enable the model to detect

relevant features, such as tonal variations and temporal nuances, crucial for sentiment analysis in audio.

5.3.2 Findings

The following are some of the evaluation metrics that we have found. The following image shows the model loss over the number of epochs during the training process

Figure 1: Model loss during training process in audio analysis

Figure 2: Confusion matrix for the audio analysis

In addition to these, here are some of the evaluation metrics that we have measured; accuracy: 90.41%, F1_score: 90.59% on the test data.

As we can see, the performance we get out of this experimentation is not that bad. Although we used a small dataset for this experiment, we actually got the best performance.

5. 4 Text Based Analysis

In this experimentation we used different pretrained models and methods to convert the audio we have to text and analyze the sentiment from the text. The main intention of this experiment is to compare our findings with the experimentation shown above. But in this experimentation, the performance depends not only on the model but on the transcription model. We have tried to use the best transcription model. As stated in the methodology section, we used a model from the Fairseq research project to transcribe audio data to text.

5.4.1 Convolution Neural Network with FastText Embedding

FastText embeddings are highly suitable for morphologically rich languages, and Afaan Oromo, with its intricate morphological structure, is no exception. Utilizing FastText embedding is expected to significantly improve the model's performance. However, it's important to note that while this

combination generally yields favorable results, there are scenarios where its effectiveness may be limited.

In our case, achieving an accuracy of 52% on both the training and test sets indicates a certain level of success, considering the limited data available. However, to further enhance the model's performance, especially in capturing more nuanced relationships within the data, there is a pressing need for more morphological complexity in the training dataset.

It's worth mentioning that the fixed nature of FastText embeddings may pose challenges in certain situations, particularly when the data demands more dynamic and context-sensitive embeddings. Therefore, for optimal results, a thoughtful examination of the dataset characteristics is recommended. Exploring potential domain-specific embeddings could be a crucial step towards improving the model's adaptability and overall performance in diverse applications. Additionally, efforts to acquire more diverse and complex data would contribute significantly to overcoming the limitations posed by the current dataset size.

5.4.2 Convolutional Neural Network with Word2Vec Embedding model

Our Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with Word2Vec embedding integrates the strengths of convolutional layers with the semantic relationships captured by Word2Vec embeddings. While Word2Vec embeddings often excel in capturing nuanced semantic information, they face challenges in handling out-of-vocabulary words effectively, particularly in specialized domains or evolving languages. The fixed vocabulary learned during training can result in suboptimal performance when the model encounters words not present in its training set.

Moreover, Word2Vec embeddings may struggle to capture contextual variations, treating each word as an isolated entity and lacking adaptability to different meanings in diverse contexts. To address these limitations and enhance the model's performance, it may be worthwhile to explore advanced embedding techniques or consider incorporating contextualized embeddings. This could empower the model to better handle the intricacies of diverse and evolving language patterns, ultimately improving its generalization capabilities.

We achieved a training accuracy of 78% and a test accuracy of 58%. It's important to note that our model lacks an embedding representation for the Afaan Oromoo language, which likely contributes to its limited generalization performance.

5.4.3 BERT

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) stands out as a potent solution for natural language processing tasks, boasting the capability to grasp bidirectional context information. In contrast to conventional embeddings like Word2Vec, BERT takes into account the complete context of a word in a sentence, facilitating an understanding of subtle nuances and context-dependent meanings. The attention mechanism within BERT empowers it to capture long-range dependencies, contributing to its remarkable efficacy across a spectrum of NLP applications.

Despite its notable success, BERT models may encounter challenges, with overfitting being a notable concern. Overfitting arises when a model becomes too attuned to the training data, incorporating its noise and outliers, and subsequently struggles to generalize to novel, unseen data. Given the substantial number of parameters in BERT models, there is an inherent vulnerability to overfitting, particularly when the training dataset is limited or lacks diversity.

Moreover, it's important to note that the BERT model achieved a commendable training accuracy of 90%, indicative of its proficiency in learning from the training dataset. However, the test accuracy, which gauges the model's performance on unseen data, currently stands at 61%. While the training accuracy reflects the model's competence in memorizing the training data, the comparatively lower test accuracy underscores the need for addressing overfitting issues and enhancing generalization capabilities to ensure robust performance across diverse datasets.

As we can see from the metrics, the BERT model is overfitting, since it is not generalizing on the unseen data.

5.5 Findings

Although we have enough data for the text processing, we still couldn't get the best performance. We were hoping that the text based analysis would yield better performance, but that couldn't be true.

5.6 Discussion

The findings highlight the importance of considering data nature and context when selecting a modality for sentiment analysis. The findings also indicate audio based analysis is performing well than text based analysis. This might be due to the grammar irregularities and written syntax error in the text data, which might lead to inconsistency. Future work could include gathering more text data to make the text based analysis more robust and also explore hybrid models, combining the strengths of audio and text representations for improved accuracy.

6. Summary

This study not only explores the linguistic intricacies of the Afaan Oromo language but also conducts sentiment analysis through two primary experiments: analyzing raw audio data and text-based analysis. The research methodology, rooted in the Design Science Research Process, addresses challenges in sentiment analysis systematically.

The analysis of raw audio data involves training a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) on spectrograms, achieving an impressive accuracy of 90.41% and an F1 score of 90.59. The effectiveness of CNNs in capturing local patterns and nuanced sentiments is highlighted. Audio preprocessing methods, including spectrogram generation and data augmentation, contribute to the success of the model.

Text-based analysis, however, presents challenges influenced by both model performance and transcription accuracy. Despite having ample data for text processing, the performance does not surpass that of the audio analysis. The findings prompt a discussion on the importance of understanding data nature and context in sentiment analysis, suggesting potential future research directions, including hybrid models for improved accuracy by combining audio and text representations.

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